

MULTISCALE COMPUTATIONAL MODEL FOR POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES UNDER IMPACT LOADING, INCLUDING ADIABATIC HEATING EFFECTS

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that significant heat generation often accompanies the high rate inelastic deformation of polymers. As the rate of deformation increases, the thermodynamic condition transitions from isothermal to adiabatic. Adiabatic conditions can be assumed for polymer matrix composites under ballistic impact loading, where local matrix temperature rises have been experimentally observed to exceed the matrix glass transition temperature. In this work, a multiscale modeling approach is used to provide insight into the effects of matrix adiabatic heating on the impact response of a triaxially braided polymer matrix composite. Unified thermo-viscoplastic constitutive equations, recently extended by the authors to i) more accurately account for tension-compression asymmetry, ii) ensure physically realistic plastic flow, and iii) ensure thermodynamic consistency, are applied at the microscale to describe the nonlinear deformation of the thermoset polymer matrix. The thermo-viscoplastic constitutive equations are implemented into the doubly-periodic generalized method of cells micromechanics framework, which is subsequently implemented into LS-DYNA as a user defined material subroutine. Local temperature rises in the matrix due to plastic dissipation are computed via the heat energy equation. The user routine, in conjunction with a subcell-based approach to approximate the mesoscale composite braid architecture as an assemblage of laminated composite subcells, is utilized to conduct simulations of quasi-static coupon tests and flat panel impact experiments conducted on a T700/Epon 862 [0°/60°/-60°] triaxially braided composite. Available experimental data is used for model characterization and validation. Impact simulation results indicate significant local temperature rises in resin rich regions in an impact event, which are expected to play a major role in the prediction of progressive damage and failure in polymer matrix composites under impact loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites (PMCs) are beginning to be used to fabricate impact resistant, energy absorbing structures such as jet engine fan blade containment systems, which are required to maintain structural integrity in the event of a blade-out. As such, there is an urgent need for constitutive models capable of simulating the deformation, progressive damage, and failure behavior of PMCs under impact loading. However, the inherent material heterogeneity and anisotropy, multiscale nature (i.e. the disparity in length scales associated with the constituent materials, the fiber tows, the braid architecture), and the complex constituent interaction complicate the development of predictive models for PMCs, particularly under impact conditions, where isothermal conditions cannot be assumed. As the duration of applied loading becomes negligible compared to the characteristic thermal diffusion time of the material, the thermodynamic condition transitions from isothermal to adiabatic. Adiabatic conditions can be assumed for PMCs subjected under ballistic impact events, where the material may experience loading for less than a microsecond.

Johnston et al. [1] recently conducted a series of flat panel impact tests on two triaxially braided PMC material systems, T700/PR520 and T700/3502, according to ASTM D8101 [2]. In the experiments,

infrared cameras were used to measure impact induced temperature rises. The material systems tested by Johnston and coworkers had the same triaxially braided carbon fiber preform, but different thermoset polymer matrices. Cycom's PR520 contains a thermoplastic toughening phase and is relatively ductile at room temperature. Hexcel's 3502 is an untoughened epoxy that is relatively brittle at room temperature compared to PR520 for similar deformation rates. The two material systems exhibited significantly different damage morphology under impact conditions for similar impact velocities due to the different matrix materials. The T700/PR520 panel displayed highly localized visible impact damage near the impact zone; local temperature rises greater than the matrix glass transition temperature were observed in resin rich regions and correlated to the localized damaged region. Unlike the T700/PR520 panel, the T700/3502 panel did not display significant visible impact damage; however, post impact test C-scan results showed significant barely visible impact damage (BVID), indicating a widespread cracking of the 3502 matrix. The T700/3502 panel displayed significantly more BVID than the T700/PR520 panel. It is evident that the material response is highly dependent upon whether the effects of strain and strain rate hardening outweigh the thermal softening in the polymer matrix.

In this work, a multiscale modeling approach is used to gain insight into the effects of adiabatic heating on the ballistic impact response of a T700/Epon 862 (T700/E862) $[0^\circ/60^\circ/-60^\circ]$ triaxially braided composite. The T700/E862 system was chosen due to the availability of i) E862 epoxy tensile, compressive, and shear test data for tests conducted over a range of strain rates and temperatures; ii) quasi-static coupon level test data; iii) flat panel impact test data. Unified thermo-viscoplastic constitutive equations [3], recently extended by the authors [4] to i) more accurately account for tension-compression asymmetry, ii) ensure physically realistic plastic flow, and iii) ensure thermodynamic consistency, are applied at the microscale to describe the nonlinear deformation of the thermoset polymer matrix. A brief overview of the governing equations and constraints on the model parameters is presented in Section 2. Section 3 describes the implementation of the unified thermo-viscoplastic formulation into the generalized method of cells (GMC) [5] micromechanics framework, which is implemented into LS-DYNA as a user defined material (UMAT). In Section 4, a subcell-based approach to approximate the mesoscale repeating unit cell (RUC) of the triaxial braid as an assemblage of laminated composite subcells is presented. In Sections 5 and 6, the subcell approach is used in conjunction with the micromechanics-based UMAT to simulate quasi-static coupon tests and flat panel impact tests conducted on the triaxially T700/E862 material system. Adiabatic impact simulation results indicate significant local temperature rises in resin rich regions. Section 7 provides a summary and describes the plans for future work, which includes incorporating fiber failure and a matrix progressive damage model into the multiscale framework.

2 POLYMER CONSTITUTIVE FORMULATION

Since carbon fibers do not exhibit significant rate dependence or inelasticity prior to failure, and are much less sensitive to temperature than typical polymer matrices, the strain rate, temperature, and pressure dependence of PMCs is primarily a manifestation of that of the matrix. In contrast to metals, for which plastic deformation is generally considered to be deviatoric, polymers can exhibit nonzero plastic dilatation. A manifestation of pressure dependent inelastic deformation in polymers is tension-compression asymmetry; the magnitude of the compressive yield stress is greater than the tensile yield stress [6]. It is therefore necessary to employ a robust thermo-viscoplastic constitutive formulation for the matrix that incorporates said effects. The unified Bodner-Partom [7] state variable viscoplasticity model, developed to model the high temperature viscoplastic response of metals, was modified by Goldberg et al. [8] to include hydrostatic stress effects, which are known to be significant in polymers. This was accomplished by modifying the Bodner-Partom plastic potential function, the square root of the second invariant of the deviatoric stress tensor, to also be dependent on hydrostatic stress, resulting in a model capable of simulating nonisochoric viscoplastic deformation. The Goldberg model employs a single scalar state variable, α , to account for the level of influence of hydrostatic stress on plastic deformation.

In previous work by the authors [3], the components of the Goldberg model [8] inelastic strain rate tensor were modified to explicitly depend on temperature based on the Arrhenius equation for nonisothermal processes. More recently, the authors [4] further extended the viscoplastic formulation

[3] to i) more accurately account for the tension-compression asymmetry observed in the response of polymeric materials; ii) ensure physically realistic plastic flow; iii) ensure nonnegative plastic dissipation, a necessary thermodynamic requirement [9]. The model [4] is unified in that a single plastic strain tensor represents all plastic deformation. Additionally, there is no defined yield surface in state variable viscoplasticity models; nonlinearity is controlled by the evolution of state variables that represent the average effects associated with the deformation mechanisms. Due to the lack of a yield surface, plastic strains are always present, but are nominal in the “elastic” deformation regime. A brief overview of the model governing equations is as follows. For more details, the reader is referred to [4].

$$f = \sqrt{J_2} + \sqrt{\gamma\sigma_{kk}^2 + \xi\sigma_{kk}} \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^I = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} = 2D_0 \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\bar{Z}}{T\sigma_e} \right)^{2n} \right] \left(\frac{S_{ij}}{2\sqrt{J_2}} + (\sqrt{\gamma} \text{sign}(\sigma_{kk}) + \xi) \delta_{ij} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$A = (\sqrt{\gamma} \text{sign}(\sigma_{kk}) + \xi) \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{Z} = \bar{Z}_1 - (\bar{Z}_1 - \bar{Z}_0) \exp(-q\varepsilon_e^I) \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_e = \sqrt{3}f = \sqrt{3J_2} + \sqrt{3\gamma\sigma_{kk}^2 + \sqrt{3}\xi\sigma_{kk}} \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{W}^I = \sigma_{ij} \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^I = \sigma_e \dot{\varepsilon}_e^I \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_e^I = \frac{\dot{\lambda}}{\sqrt{3}} = \sqrt{\frac{2\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^I \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^I}{3(1+6A^2)}} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^I \dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^I} \quad (7)$$

In Equation 1, f is the plastic potential function, J_2 is the second invariant of the deviatoric stress tensor, and γ and ξ are nonnegative constants introduced to control the level of influence of hydrostatic stress, σ_{kk} , on plastic deformation. The use of two hydrostatic constants is necessary to allow the tensile and compressive plastic Poisson's ratios, and therefore the magnitudes of the tensile and compressive yield stresses, to be varied independently, which is not possible with a single hydrostatic constant or state variable. An associative flow rule is assumed, where the components of the inelastic strain rate tensor, $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^I$, are assumed to be equal to the product of the scalar rate of the plastic multiplier, $\dot{\lambda}$, with the partial derivative of the plastic potential function, f , with respect to the Cauchy stress tensor components, σ_{ij} . In Equations 2-7, D_0 is a constant that represents the maximum inelastic strain rate and essentially acts as a scale factor, T is the absolute (Kelvin) temperature, S_{ij} are the components of the deviatoric stress tensor, n is a constant that controls strain rate sensitivity, \bar{Z} is a temperature dependent isotropic state variable that represents the resistance to internal stress at a given temperature (captures strain hardening), q is a constant that controls the hardening rate, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, and σ_e is the effective stress. It should be noted that the effective stress is *defined* such that it is equal to the applied stress in a uniaxial tensile or uniaxial compressive stress state; the effective inelastic strain rate, $\dot{\varepsilon}_e^I$, is then *derived* based on the principal of equivalence of plastic work rate density (Equation 6), which must be nonnegative (nonnegative plastic dissipation). The effective inelastic strain rate, $\dot{\varepsilon}_e^I$, and the components of the inelastic strain rate tensor, $\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^I$, are integrated forward in time to determine the total accumulated effective inelastic strain, ε_e^I , and the inelastic strain tensor components, ε_{ij}^I . The evolution of the state variable \bar{Z} from its initial value of \bar{Z}_0 to its final value of \bar{Z}_1 is driven by the accumulated effective inelastic strain according to Equation 4. In this research, infinitesimal deformations are assumed; as such, the total strain tensor is additively decomposed into the sum of the elastic, inelastic, and thermal components.

2.1 Nonnegative Plastic Dissipation

Nonnegative plastic dissipation is a necessary thermodynamic requirement [9] that must be enforced. It is apparent that the effective inelastic strain rate (Equation 7) is always nonnegative whereas, depending on the stress state and the values of the hydrostatic constants, γ and ξ , the effective stress can achieve a positive, zero, or negative value, the latter resulting in negative plastic dissipation (Equation 6). The following relationship, determined in the authors' previous work [4], guarantees nonnegative plastic dissipation.

$$\xi \leq \sqrt{\gamma} \quad (8)$$

2.2 Plastic Poisson's Ratios

The tensile (or compressive) plastic Poisson's ratio is defined as the negative ratio of transverse to longitudinal *plastic* strain (or plastic strain rates) in a uniaxial tensile (or compressive) stress state. Expressions for the tensile and compressive plastic Poisson's ratios, $\nu^{p,T}$ and $\nu^{p,C}$, as functions of the hydrostatic constants were derived using Equation 2 in previous work by the authors [4] and are shown below.

$$\nu^{p,T} = \frac{\sqrt{3} - 6A_{UT}}{2\sqrt{3} + 6A_{UT}} \quad (9)$$

$$A_{UT} = \sqrt{\gamma} + \xi \quad (10)$$

$$\nu^{p,C} = \frac{\sqrt{3} + 6A_{UC}}{2\sqrt{3} - 6A_{UC}} \quad (11)$$

$$A_{UC} = -\sqrt{\gamma} + \xi \quad (12)$$

In Equations 9-12, A_{UT} and A_{UC} are the values of A (Equation 3) for uniaxial tensile and uniaxial compressive stress states. Refs. [10-11] suggest that the tensile and compressive plastic Poisson's ratios for an isotropic material must be between 0 and 0.5. By manipulating Equations 9 and 11, the bounds obtained for A_{UT} and A_{UC} to guarantee tensile and compressive plastic Poisson's ratios between 0 and 0.5 are given by Equations 13 and 14. The hydrostatic constants must be determined such that Equations 8, 13, and 14 are not violated.

$$0 \leq A_{UT} \leq \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} \quad (13)$$

$$-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} \leq A_{UC} \leq 0 \quad (14)$$

2.3 Adiabatic Heating

To accurately predict thermal softening behavior in the matrix of textile PMCs subjected to ballistic impact, temperature rises due to inelastic deformation are computed via the heat energy equation, which governs the interdependence between mechanical deformation and spatial-temporal temperature variation.

$$k\nabla^2 T - \alpha_M(3\lambda + 2\mu)T\dot{\epsilon}_{kk}^e + \beta\boldsymbol{\sigma}:\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}^I = \rho C\dot{T} \quad (15)$$

In Equation 15, k is the thermal conductivity, α_M is the coefficient of thermal expansion, λ and μ are Lamé's constants, $\dot{\epsilon}_{kk}^e$ is the elastic volumetric strain rate, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}^I$ is the inelastic strain rate tensor, ρ is the density, C is the specific heat, and β is the inelastic heat fraction, which represents the fraction of plastic work converted to heat. Due to their rapid nature, adiabatic

conditions can be assumed for PMCs under ballistic impact conditions. Since the adiabatic assumption implies no heat transfer, the conduction term in Equation 15 is ignored. Additionally, as is often done [12], it is assumed that the thermoelastic term is negligible compared to the thermoplastic term. Considering the aforementioned assumptions, the heat energy equation reduces to:

$$\dot{T} = \frac{\beta \sigma : \dot{\epsilon}^I}{\rho C} \quad (16)$$

Assuming the inelastic heat fraction is known, either assumed or measured experimentally, Equation 16 is integrated forward in time to compute temperature rises due to plastic dissipation at each timestep an incremental solution. Note that, according to Equations 6 and 16, negative plastic dissipation implies a decrease in temperature with inelastic deformation, which is nonphysical.

2.4 Temperature Dependence of Elastic Properties

The elastic properties of polymers are known to exhibit significant strain rate and temperature dependence. To approximate the matrix elastic properties at various strain rates and temperatures, an approach similar to the decompose-shift-reconstruct (DSR) method used by Mulliken and Boyce [13] is utilized. The approach is based on shifting neat resin dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) data with strain rate. Since a DMA test is conducted at a particular frequency, rate dependent shifts in the dynamic moduli can be quantified by conducting a series of DMA tests, each at a different frequency. Figure 1 illustrates the shifting methodology for E862 DMA data [14]. In this work, it is assumed that the matrix shear modulus is equal to the shear storage modulus and that Poisson's ratio (elastic) is independent of temperature. This allows matrix elastic properties to be computed based on the rate of applied deformation and the current matrix temperature (Equation 16). It should be noted that, as shown in Figure 1, the glass transition temperature range is train rate dependent.

Figure 1: Illustration of shifting of Epon 862 epoxy DMA data [14] with strain rate.

2.5 Determination of Unified Thermo-viscoplasticity Model Constants

The unified thermo-viscoplastic formulation model has been calibrated in previous work by the authors [4] using neat Epon 862 (E862) resin tensile, shear, and compression data from tests conducted over a range of strain rates and temperatures. The E862 material properties and viscoplastic model parameters are shown in Table 1. A detailed procedure for determining the model constants will be presented in a future report. The values of the hydrostatic constants correspond to tensile and compressive plastic Poisson's ratios of 0.38 and 0.5, respectively.

Table 1: Epon 862 Material Properties and Viscoplastic Model Parameters.

Property/Parameter	Value	Property/Parameter	Value
Young's Modulus	*DMA*	n	0.6351
Poisson's Ratio	0.4	q	74.4073
Density (kg/m ³)	1,200	γ	0.0006
Specific Heat (J/kg-K)	1,260	ξ	0.0245
CTE (1/K)	5.4e-5	$Z_0(T)$ (Pa-K)	$-(1.462e9)T + 7.421e11$
D_0 (s ⁻¹)	10 ⁶	$Z_1(T)$ (Pa-K)	$-(2.365e9)T + 1.232e12$

3 MICROMECHANICAL MODELING

To simulate the effective behavior of a unidirectional (UD) composite, including the effects of local matrix adiabatic heating and subsequent thermal softening, the unified thermo-viscoplastic constitutive formulation described in Section 2 is implemented into the GMC micromechanics framework [5]. The implemented doubly-periodic microscale GMC RUC, shown in Figure 2, consists of one fiber and three matrix microscale subcells, where V_f denotes the fiber volume fraction. The multiscale approach is advantageous in that it allows adiabatic heating to be modeled at the matrix constituent level, where it has been experimentally observed to be predominant in flat panel impact experiments [1]. Microscale matrix subcell level temperature rates are determined from the respective microscale subcell inelastic heat fraction, density, specific heat, and plastic work rate density (Equation 16) and are integrated forward in time to compute the microscale subcell temperatures. At each timestep in an incremental solution procedure, the matrix subcell elastic properties are updated to reflect current temperature using the shifting approach described in Section 2.4. Note the carbon fibers are modeled as transversely isotropic and linearly elastic. Additionally, the temperature dependence of the fiber elastic properties ($E_1=230$ GPa, $E_2=15$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.2$, $\nu_{23}=0.3$, $G_{12}=27$ GPa) has not been considered in this work.

Figure 2: Schematic of four subcell GMC microscale RUC.

The four subcell GMC micromechanics model, with the unified thermo-viscoplastic constitutive formulation applied to matrix microscale subcells, has been implemented into LS-DYNA as a UMAT. The next section describes the use of the UMAT in conjunction with a subcell-based approach to approximate material heterogeneity at the highest analysis length scale.

4 SUBCELL METHODOLOGY

As aforementioned, the material system under investigation in this study is a T700/Epon 862 [0°/60°/-60°] triaxially braided composite. The triaxially braided carbon fiber preform (no resin), shown in Figure 3a, consists of 24K tows in the axial direction (red arrow) and 12K tows in the bias/braider (blue arrows) directions. Experimental evidence has shown [15] that when braided composites are subjected to ballistic impact, the damage often progresses along the tow directions. This architecturally dependent damage morphology is due to the relatively large size of the mesoscale RUC (dimensions shown in Figure 3b) compared to the size of structural components.

To approximate the braid architecture at the highest analysis length scale, a subcell-based approach, illustrated in Figure 3, is utilized. Once the mesoscale RUC is identified (Figure 3b), it is discretized in-plane into unique mesoscale subcell regions based on presence of axial and/or braider tows. As shown in Figure 3d, the subcell regions are then discretized through-thickness into unique composite laminates, with ply orientations determined from the braid architecture. The subcell discretization shown in Figure 3d is known as the absorbed matrix model (AMM) [16], since braider plies are assumed to be

homogenized representations of the braider tows and surrounding resin rich regions. It should be noted that, with the AMM discretization, there is no bias tow continuity.

In this work, a multiscale approach is taken, where the mesoscale subcell UD layers strains are taken as global strains applied to a microscale RUC (Figures 2 and 3d). The GMC micromechanics theory is then used to localize the UD layer strains to the microscale subcell level to compute the stresses and strains in the fibers and matrix; homogenization is then performed to compute the microscale RUC effective stresses, which are taken to be the stresses in the UD layers of the mesoscale subcells.

To determine the dimensions of the UD layers of the mesoscale subcells, optical microscopy measurements are combined with measurements taken from the triaxially braided carbon fiber preform (Figure 3a). The width of mesoscale subcells A and C is equal to the width of the axial tows, which was determined by averaging measurements of the widths of several axial tows in the triaxially braided carbon fiber preform (Figure 3a). The average measured value was approximately 5.1 mm. Based on the total width of the mesoscale RUC (17.8 mm), the width of mesoscale subcells B and D is 3.8 mm. The length of the mesoscale RUC, shown in Figure 3d, is 5.1 mm. The mesoscale RUC height was determined from a 3.175 thick triaxially braided panel consisting of six layers of preform through the thickness; since one mesoscale RUC corresponds to one layer of carbon fiber preform, the height of the mesoscale RUC is taken as 0.529 mm. Since the axial tows contain twice as many carbon fibers as the bias tows, the axial plies were assumed to be twice the thickness as the bias tows in subcells A and C. The inner UD layers of the mesoscale subcells B and D are also assumed to have twice the thickness as the outer (i.e. top and bottom) UD layers.

To determine the fiber volume fractions of the UD layers, optical micrographs were taken within the axial tows. A script was written to compute the average fiber volume fraction from 261 micrographs; the average fiber volume fraction for the axial tows was 65.6%, which is assumed to be the fiber volume fraction of the axial plies in subcells A and C. The fiber volume fractions of the bias tows in subcells A/C and B/D were determined to be 54.4% and 50.7%, respectively, based on the subcell dimensions, knowledge of the axial ply fiber volume fraction, and knowledge of the overall composite fiber volume fraction of 56%.

Figure 3: a) Triaxially braided carbon fiber preform with RUC shown; b) Enlarged image of identified RUC with dimensions shown; c) Identification of four adjacent subcell regions; d) Discretization of each subcell through its thickness into an approximation of unidirectional plies.

5 QUASI STATIC STRAIGHT-SIDED COUPON SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, quasi-static tensile tests conducted on the T700/E862 [17] material system are simulated and compared to available experimental data. In the axial and transverse tension tests, specimens were loaded parallel and perpendicular to the axial tow direction. The coupons used in the experiments were 304.8 mm in length, 35.8 mm in width, 3.175 mm in thickness, and had a gage length of 203.2 mm. Each physical coupon had six through-thickness layers of triaxially braided preform. The experiments were conducted in displacement control at a displacement rate of 0.0106 mm/sec until specimen failure.

The axial and transverse tensile coupon finite element (FE) meshes, shown in Figures 4a and 5a, were spatially discretized with 1920 and 1932 thick shell elements (LS-DYNA ELFORM=5: Assumed strain reduced integration), respectively, each with three through-thickness integration points and LS-DYNA type 6 hourglass control. The mesoscale RUC is indicated in Figures 4a and 5a with a red

rectangle. In the meshes shown, each mesoscale subcell is modeled as a thick shell element with three through thickness integration layers, each corresponding to a UD ply. Six thick shell elements were used through the thickness of each coupon mesh to represent each of the six layers of preform in the physical coupons. No contact was used between element layers (elements of adjacent layers share nodes) and only the coupon gage sections were modeled. In the simulations, all degrees of freedom of the nodes on one end of the specimen were constrained; the nodes on the other end were only permitted to move in the loading direction. The same displacement rate used in the tests was used in the simulations. Due to the nominal nodal accelerations, mass scaling was applied to achieve a reasonable timestep in the explicit FE simulations. Additionally, due to the quasi-static loading rate, no adiabatic heating is expected and isothermal conditions can be assumed to apply. Therefore, the results from this section are from isothermal simulations (inelastic heat fraction equal to zero).

The simulated stress-strain curves for the axial and transverse tensile coupon tests superimposed with the experimental data [17] is shown in Figures 4b and 5b, respectively. Since damage and failure have not yet been incorporated into the multiscale framework, the end of the simulated stress-strain curves should not be interpreted as predicted coupon failure. The simulated axial tensile stress-strain response is in excellent agreement with the experimental data. The simulated transverse tensile stress-strain response is initially in agreement with the experimental data, but fails to capture the nonlinearity observed in the test. The nonlinear response observed in straight-sided transverse tensile tests on triaxially braided composites has been attributed [18] to edge damage (transverse splitting) in the axial tows, which terminate at the free edge. A notched geometry was suggested to mitigate said effects [18].

Figure 4: a) Axial tension FE mesh; b) Simulated and experimental axial tensile stress-strain curves.

Figure 5: a) Transverse tension FE mesh; b) Simulated and experimental transverse tensile stress-strain curves.

6 FLAT PANEL IMPACT SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate the effects of adiabatic heating on the impact response of the T700/E862 triaxially braided material system, a flat panel impact test conducted according to ASTM D8101 [2] is simulated and compared to experimental data provided by [19]. Since damage and failure are not currently incorporated in the multiscale framework, projectile penetration cannot currently be simulated. Therefore, an impact experiment for which acceptable DIC data is available and no projectile penetration occurred is simulated. The initial velocity and initial temperature in the test are 163.058 m/s and 21°C; the same values are used in the simulations. In the experiments, the composite panels are square with side lengths of 30.48 cm, a thickness of 3.175 mm, and six layers of triaxially braided carbon fiber preform through the thickness. The panels are held in place with a 25.4 cm circular fixture while they are impacted at the center of the ungripped circular region with a cylindrical, spherical nose aluminum projectile.

The flat panel FE mesh used for impact analysis is shown in Figure 6a, where the mesoscale RUC is denoted with a red rectangle and the blue square is the region of the FE mesh corresponding to the region monitored by DIC in the experiments. Figures 6b-6d show the simulated and experimental out-of-plane displacement time history for three points shown in Figure 6a (Point 1, Point 2, Center Section). Time $t=0$ ms corresponds to the time of impact. Simulations have been conducted with inelastic heat fractions of zero and unity, which correspond to isothermal and fully adiabatic conditions.

According to Figures 6b-6d, the out-of-plane displacements predicted by the isothermal and adiabatic simulations are nearly identical; it is hypothesized that this is due to fact that damage and failure are not yet incorporated into the analysis. In Figure 6b, note the experimental out-of-plane displacement curve stops at approximately 0.15 ms due to a loss of paint required by the DIC. The simulated and experimental out-of-plane displacement-time plots for Point1 and Point 2, shown in Figures 6c and 6d, are in good agreement up to just before the first peak, after which they become out of phase. It is hypothesized that this occurs due to matrix damage and fiber failure in the experiment, which is not currently captured in the models. Even in impact tests where the projectile penetration does not occur, there is still significant impact damage, both visible and barely visible. This impact damage effectively reduces the effective wave speed of the material in damaged areas, which means the average time it takes the initial stress wave to propagate from the center of the panel to the circular boundary in the experiment is less than the time it takes for the reflected stress wave to propagate from the circular boundary back to the center of the panel (since it has to traverse damaged areas with lower effective wave speeds than nondamaged areas). Since the simulation does not yet contain progressive damage or fiber failure, the effective wave speed of the composite model after the first impact is likely higher than it should be, which is why the simulated peaks in out-of-plane displacement occur before the experimental peaks.

Figure 7 shows the experimental and simulated out-of-plane displacement contours on the back side of the panel (i.e. the side of the panel not impacted by projectile) at various times after impact. Results are shown for the adiabatic impact simulation (inelastic heat fraction equal to unity). Note that the white spaces on the experimental contour plots are due to loss of the speckle pattern required by the DIC to compute the Z-displacement. Excellent agreement between the simulation and the experiment are obtained up to 0.15 ms.

Figure 6: a) Panel mesh. Experimental and simulated out-of-plane displacement time histories for b) Center Point; c) Point 1; d) Point 2.

Time after impact (ms)	0.01	0.05	0.15
Experimental			
Simulation			
	Z-displacement 8.712e-04 7.828e-04 6.944e-04 6.060e-04 5.177e-04 4.293e-04 3.409e-04 2.525e-04 1.641e-04 7.569e-05 -1.270e-05	Z-displacement 6.477e-03 5.819e-03 5.161e-03 4.503e-03 3.846e-03 3.188e-03 2.530e-03 1.872e-03 1.214e-03 5.563e-04 -1.016e-04	Z-displacement 1.389e-02 1.309e-02 1.228e-02 1.148e-02 1.067e-02 9.868e-03 9.063e-03 8.258e-03 7.452e-03 6.647e-03 5.842e-03

Figure 7: Simulated and experimental out-of-plane displacement contours for various times after impact. Results are shown for the adiabatic impact simulation (inelastic heat fraction equal to unity).

Figure 8 show simulated contours of the maximum value of the microscale subcell absolute temperature (Kelvin) 0.15 milliseconds after impact for each of the six through thickness layers of thick shell elements. Layer 1 designates the layer impacted by the projectile whereas layer 6 denotes the backside of the plate. It is evident that the highest temperature rises occur in the middle two layers, with the maximum temperature of 406.2 Kelvin (133.05°C, 271.49°F) occurring in the 4th layer of thick shell elements. It is also interesting to note that the simulation predicts higher temperature rises on the back layer than the layer the projectile comes into contact with.

Figure 8: Contours of maximum microscale subcell level temperature rise on various layers in the adiabatic impact simulation 0.15 milliseconds after impact; layer 1 designates the layer impacted by the projectile whereas layer 6 denotes the backside of the plate.

7 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Details regarding a multiscale computational investigation into the effects of adiabatic heating on the ballistic impact response of a T700/E862 $[0^\circ/60^\circ/-60^\circ]$ triaxially braided composite have been presented. At the highest analysis length scale, a subcell-based approach was used to approximate the triaxially braided mesoscale RUC into an assemblage of laminated composite subcell regions. Mesoscale composite subcells were modeled in LS-DYNA as thick shell elements, where through thickness integration points represent UD mesoscale subcell layers. The GMC micromechanics theory, implemented into LS-DYNA as a UMAT, is used to localize integration point strains to a microscale GMC RUC consisting of one fiber and three matrix microscale subcells. The fibers were modeled as transversely isotropic and linear elastic whereas unified thermo-viscoplastic constitutive equations were employed to describe the rate, temperature, and pressure dependent evolution of the inelastic deformation in the E862 polymer matrix. Temperature rises due to the conversion of plastic work to heat were computed at the microscale subcell level. A technique based on shifting DMA data was used to compute the matrix elastic properties over a range of strain rates and temperatures. The UMAT, in conjunction with the subcell approach, was used to simulate quasi-static coupon tests and flat panel impact tests conducted on the T700/E862 material system. Isothermal and adiabatic impact simulations showed almost identical out-of-plane displacement time histories for the three points analyzed, likely because progressive damage and failure have not yet been incorporated into the multiscale framework. The predicted out-of-plane displacement time histories were in good agreement with the experimental data up to the first peak in the displacement-time plot, after which the response appears to be too stiff, which is also likely due to the lack of damage and failure in the methodology. The adiabatic impact simulation predicted local matrix temperatures of greater than 110°C just 0.15 ms after impact, which would likely significantly affect the predicted material response if fiber subcells were permitted to fail. Current work in progress is focused on the incorporation of fiber failure into the multiscale framework and the development of a progressive damage model to simulate the initiation and propagation of matrix damage. It is expected that, when progressive damage and failure is incorporated into the analysis, accounting for the effects of adiabatic heating in the polymer matrix will result in more accurate model predictions.

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